

Report on the DRI Mapping Survey

Authors:

Ag Stephens, Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, RAL Space, STFC

Gabin Kayumbi Kabeya, Scientific Computing Department, STFC

Simon Lambert, Scientific Computing Department, STFC

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Executive Summary

Introduction and Aims

The UKRI digital research infrastructure (DRI) represents a vast and diverse range of systems, people and activities that is inherently difficult to measure. The UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project took on the task of gathering a representative sample of DRI facilities with the aim of understanding what the DRI looks like, along with a range of properties that relate to its wider carbon footprint. It is expected that future activities within this remit will require a database of all significant DRI assets in terms of their technical specification, energy usage, efficiency measures and user communities. Capturing a timeline of this information will allow analysts to compare different systems in order to identify opportunities for positive change.

The work was carried out by a team of Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) staff from the Scientific Computing and RAL Space Departments.

Methodology

The first phase of the work was to compile a list of DRI facilities. This work was done by interrogating the UKRI InfraPortal records and knowledge of project partners, to identify relevant facilities and their contact points. After an in-depth process, the final count of facilities to survey was 123.

The next stage involved developing a comprehensive questionnaire to be emailed out to each of the facility managers/contacts. A questionnaire was developed, in conjunction with the wider team in the scoping project, with sections focussed on (1) Contact and facility info, (2) Funding and community, (3) General characteristics, (4) Technical details, (5) Energy supply, (6) Energy usage, (7) Environmental considerations and constraints, (8) User engagement and (9) Other information and feedback. Since we were aware that the DRI is highly diverse, it was likely that some questions were not applicable, so they were phrased in a manner that would allow respondents to provide simple answers, or to elaborate on details or relevance. A number of case studies were carried out in the project, the information from these also fed into the design of the questions.

A Google Form was chosen as the technology to deliver the survey, as it was free and simple to use, and the results could be easily converted to CSV or Excel formats. The questionnaire was tested on a small sample of colleagues who run DRI facilities, and their feedback was used in developing the final version. The survey was carried out between November and January 2023, with recipients being contacted via e-mail, and in-person where they were known to the team.

An Expert Advisory Group (EAG) was created to help the project team decide on the most appropriate way of analysing sharing the results of the survey. The key recommendations from the EAG were that (1) an internal database would be analysed for the main results, (2) a public dataset would be generated with anonymised and categorised responses, (3) the public dataset would be published alongside metadata and guidance on how to use it, including an interactive Jupyter Notebook demonstrating how to read and visualise the dataset.

The responses were exported to a CSV file and processed to improve the quality of the dataset. The transformation of the original responses through to the public dataset included the following steps: anonymisation, exclusion of irrelevant fields/records, mapping of answers to categories or numerical bins, handling of missing values, outlier checking, correlation checking and summarisation of free-text responses.

Results, Key Findings and Recommendations

Of the 123 facilities contacted, 51 responses were received, and 7 of those were excluded as not being appropriate or relevant to the DRI dataset. The results therefore consisted of 44 valid records.

The results were reviewed, analysed and are presented in the report in a series of pie charts. The key findings were extracted and mapped to a set of 20 recommendations. The findings and recommendations can be grouped into the following topics:

- Defining the DRI
- Engaging the community
- Disseminating knowledge and best practice
- Creating a database of DRI information
- Innovating and supporting the community
- Net Zero policy and strategy
- Undertaking further research

Within the scope of **defining the DRI**, it is imperative that a consistent and reliable picture of the physical DRI is found, either from a system-wide survey or other methods such as sampling and modelling. Given the variability in the DRI, it is important to categorise the DRI facilities by a defined set of metrics. Additionally, to avoid missing parts of the UKRI carbon footprint, we must ensure partially UKRI-funded resources are appropriately captured.

Regarding **engagement of the community**, the level of engagement with each component of the DRI should reflect its size and relative impact. It was identified that some UKRI DRI facilities are already collecting data relevant to their carbon footprint and are keen to engage. UKRI should work with the contacts made within the DRI Mapping process to explore the most effective ways of maintaining and evolving community engagement to build the DRI database required in future. Incentives, such as funding and support, should be considered to foster engagement. It is also important that direct contact is made with each Research Council in future engagement to ensure full coverage of the DRI.

In terms of **disseminating knowledge and best practice**, a centralised service or hub should be created to gather best practice and promote positive change. It is important to share the experiences of those parts of the DRI community that have committed to using renewable energy, and to consider whether UKRI should consider a policy of purchasing electricity from renewable sources across the entire DRI. Additionally, some respondents are re-using waste heat, so their knowledge and experience should be shared with other facilities. Since a variety of energy usage monitoring currently takes place, support should be given to facility managers to enable them to develop and deploy systems for monitoring and reporting energy usage. Information, support and training is essential to bring about the change required to meet the Net Zero target, this needs to focus on understanding and approaches for more sustainable practices (at all levels).

In relation to the **creation of a database of DRI information**, it is important to create standards for recording and reporting energy usage and efficiency. A public database of key information about the UKRI DRI should be collected and updated routinely. The measurement of annual energy usage should be a fundamental measure recorded in the database.

Regarding **innovation and support**, a fair approach should be developed for recording, monitoring and reporting energy usage information at multiple levels (e.g. per job, user or project). Once a

comprehensive dataset exists, then UKRI should investigate whether larger facilities bring about more efficient use of DRI, and if so, make arrangements for greater centralisation of infrastructure and services.

In terms of **Net Zero policy and strategy**, there has been a great deal of good will and interest in making changes towards a lower carbon footprint from both users and managers of DRI facilities. Net Zero needs to become an explicit and significant concern for all in the UKRI community. It should be embedded in all layers of the organisation, and there should be suitable recognition, acknowledgement, and reward for positive action towards sustainability.

Regarding **further research**, the relative contribution of three areas requires more investigation: personal devices (e.g. laptops, tablets, and phones), digital networks (i.e. the physical networking infrastructure) and use of public cloud computing and storage. These were considered outside the scope of the DRI Mapping Survey and have not been estimated in terms of how they compare to the DRI facilities. UKRI needs more data on the impact and trends of energy usage related to each of these.

Conclusion

Mapping the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure was a complex and involved task. There is no clear delineation of what the DRI is, and there is great variety in terms of the size, purpose, function and usage of the components of the DRI. Whilst some major parts of the DRI are already engaged with the Net Zero agenda, others are lacking information and training to be able to assess their carbon footprint. The work outlined in this report demonstrates a pathfinder process that is essential for UKRI to accurately monitor and improve its energy usage and progress towards the Net Zero target. The generation of a list of the significant DRI Facilities is a pre-requisite to capturing the current situation. Furthermore, establishing a methodology for measuring or modelling the long tail of small facilities and personal compute is also required. The results and inferences within this work highlight the value of collecting and sharing information about the DRI to draw out best practice and opportunities for knowledge-exchange. Building a more comprehensive database of this information, and capturing temporal updates, will be essential for UKRI to reach Net Zero by 2040.

1 Introduction

1.1 What is the UKRI DRI?

The United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI) defines the building blocks of the digital research infrastructure¹ (DRI) system as including:

- large scale compute facilities, including high-throughput, high-performance, and cloud computing
- data storage facilities, repositories, stewardship and security
- software and shared code libraries
- mechanisms for access, such as networks and user authentication systems
- people: the users, and the experts who develop and maintain these powerful resources.

The UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project² aims to produce a clear roadmap for how UKRI can take action to achieve its commitment to becoming net zero by 2040. Within the project, a number of activities, and sub-projects, are looking in detail at different aspects of the DRI.

From the perspective of the DRI Mapping activity, we focussed on the *facilities* that make up the DRI as a common unit that should be measurable across different parts of the digital landscape. This means that some aspects of the DRI are not being recorded. These are discussed in the [gaps section](#) later in the document.

1.2 Why map the DRI?

The UKRI DRI represents a vast and diverse range of systems, people and activities that is inherently difficult to measure. However, it is essential to build a representative picture of *the DRI* so that the impact of future changes in policy and practice can be compared against the current situation. In this project, we attempt to gather a representative sample of DRI facilities with the aim that it provides a foundation upon which future activities can be built. It is very likely that UKRI will need to maintain a database of its significant digital assets in terms of their energy usage along with a range of technical details that will allow analysts to compare and contrast different systems in order to identify opportunities for positive change.

1.3 Document overview

This document outlines the process undertaken the in DRI Mapping task. It provides a description of the methodology, an analysis of the results of a DRI Facilities survey and moves on to discussions and recommendations to feed back to the core project.

2 Methodology

2.1 The Team

The DRI Mapping task was managed by:

- Ag Stephens (CEDA)
- Gabin Kayumbi Kabeya (SCD)
- Simon Lambert (SCD)

¹ <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-offer/creating-world-class-research-and-innovation-infrastructure/digital-research-infrastructure/>

² <https://net-zero-dri.ceda.ac.uk/>

Additional help was received from the core project team, the wider project partners, and the community of facility managers who gave their time to interact with our survey.

2.2 Gathering requirements

This work was driven by the high-level project milestones:

- **MS4:** Mapping the energy consumption patterns and models of operation and service delivery for all UKRI-owned and majority funded DRI.
- **MS6:** UKRI DRI Carbon landscape database to inform the final report and provide a resource for stakeholders.

From early discussions with the core team it was decided that a questionnaire should be built that would be used for a survey of DRI facilities. The content of the questionnaire was iterated over during a period of discussion with the various project partners. The aim was to incorporate a range of different perspectives including general information about the funding and scientific usage, technical characteristics, energy supply and usage, engagement with environmental considerations, user interactions and other miscellaneous questions.

A draft questionnaire was shared with the partners and feedback was gathered and integrated through an Excel spreadsheet. The team then went through each item of feedback and responded to it by adjusting the questionnaire as appropriate.

2.3 Compiling a list of DRI facilities

There is no official list of UKRI DRI facilities. The shared funding and shared resources also make it hard to delineate what is considered a *UKRI* facility. We have used the following definition in this work:

1. Facilities are in-scope if they are *UKRI-owned or majority-funded*.

The agreed approach for building a list of DRI facilities was as follows:

1. Extract a filtered list of "e-infrastructure and data" contacts from the UKRI InfraPortal³.
Count: 465.
2. Send out a brief survey to each of the facilities identified in (1) to check:
 - a. The entity is a relevant facility
 - b. The contact details are appropriate for our main survey

Count: 109

3. Request input from the community to identify more facilities, via:
 - a. The core team, sandpit projects, steering committee.
 - b. STFC contacts, known to the team.
 - c. E-mail requests to individuals and groups.
 - d. Presentation, information posters and one-to-one contacts at the Computing Insight UK 2022 conference⁴.

Count: 123

From this process we gathered a **final list of 123 UKRI DRI facilities**.

³ <https://www.infraportal.org.uk/>

⁴ <https://www.scd.stfc.ac.uk/Pages/CIUK2022.aspx>

2.4 Designing the questionnaire

2.4.1 Content

As discussed in the [requirements section](#), the content of the questionnaire was built up iteratively following many interactions with different stakeholders within the project and beyond. The questions were grouped into sections in order to provide context for the respondent. The questions were intentionally framed to cope with a variety of responses that might be either:

1. **Very specific:** such as a single number, or a category
2. **Complex:** represented by free text which may include specific information that could be extracted during analysis

The level of prior knowledge, and of information available to each respondent was likely to vary greatly. We therefore adopted an approach to many questions that allowed either no answer, short answers, or elaboration as required. This multi-level approach is outlined in figure 1. The

Figure 1. Approach used to engage respondents at the level they were able to answer.

The team was conducting some DRI case studies in parallel (investigating facilities: JASMIN, Scafell Pike and JADE2). The interviews with the facility managers and discussions within those groups also informed the contents of the questionnaire.

The sections covered in the questionnaire were as follows:

1. Contact and facility info
2. Funding and community
3. General characteristics
4. Technical details
5. Energy supply
6. Energy usage
7. Environmental considerations and constraints
8. User engagement
9. Other information, opportunity for feedback, and conclusion

2.4.2 Communication and technology choices

Since we needed to contact hundreds of people on a number of occasions, an automated e-mail approach was taken for disseminating the survey information and sending out reminders. All

messages included contact information so that recipients could communicate directly with the team via the CEDA Helpdesk.

The use of Google Forms⁵ was considered an appropriate technology for the survey because:

- The team had experience of using it
- It could scale to hundreds of users
- It was provided for free
- Results could be exported directly to various formats (such as CSV)
- Multiple sections could be provided as pages, each containing relevant questions
- It could handle different question formats, such as multiple choice, free text and optional questions
- It could be branded/styled as required
- The results could be quickly graphed using the tool dashboard

2.5 Testing the questionnaire

Before being distributed widely, the questionnaire was shared with some STFC contacts in order to test the format, structure and web-tool. They provided feedback which was assimilated into the final version of the questionnaire.

2.6 Final questionnaire

The final version of the questionnaire is was published at this link: <https://bit.ly/netzerodri> (NO LONGER ACCESSIBLE). [Appendix 1](#) lists the sections and questions in full.

2.7 Carrying out the survey

2.7.1 Communication and timeline

The survey was first opened and recipients were e-mailed on 15th November 2022. The closing date was planned for 24th December 2022 but this was extended due to a relatively low initial response and some messages from recipients requesting more time. Follow-up messages were sent on 24th November, 8th December and 19th December 2022.

Following some late responses in January, the survey was closed on 31st January 2023. Following that, a few responses were received by e-mail and were added to the final table of responses.

2.8 Analysis

2.8.1 Expert Advisory Group

An important aspect of the questionnaire design was the consideration of the data that would be generated by the results, how it could be analysed, interpreted and shared. An important factor is that the overarching project will be providing recommendations for a roadmap to achieve Net Zero.

It was agreed that an Expert Advisory Group (EAG) should be convened from contacts within the project with the task of agreeing how the data should be handled and shared with the project and wider community. The interaction with the EAG was invaluable in highlighting certain issues and helping to steer this part of the project towards outcomes that will be both practical and meaningful. The key decisions and actions ratified by the EAG involvement were as follows:

⁵ <https://docs.google.com/forms>

1. Export the results to CSV:
 - a. this is the "internal" database (DB)
2. Map the results to a CSV - probably manually:
 - a. this is the "public" dataset
 - b. column names will be codified (I.e. converted from sentences to short codes)
 - c. many answers will be categorised/binned in order to aid analysis and visualisation extracting numerical data from text
 - d. numeric, or short text, answers will be extracted from longer responses when embedded in text
 - e. check for outliers, and remove if erroneous
 - f. remove long answers where appropriate
 - g. clean up heterogeneous responses
3. Use Jupyter Notebooks to analyse the data and generate graphs, charts and tables
 - a. Put the underlying code in a public GitHub repository
4. Analyse interesting responses, correlations, data points etc.
5. Make contact with the facility managers who did not complete the questionnaire:
 - a. Gather information about what prevented them from responding
 - b. Create recommendations for how to get better engagement in future iterations
6. Generate a draft report that discusses:
 - a. key findings
 - b. specific issues and findings
 - c. gaps identified from the survey
7. Share the draft report with the core team
8. From the draft report, generate the final report which:
 - a. is compliant with our data protection statement
9. Publish the public report to relevant channels
10. Publish the public dataset as a CSV file on Zenodo
 - a. Before publication:
 - i. seek advice on the wording of a disclaimer
 - ii. ensure the disclaimer says that the data are unverified and that users should check the figures before publishing any analysis
 - b. Include guidance on interpretation:
 - i. State that data are not verified
 - ii. Provide a table of the full questionnaire questions (and answer options), and how they have been processed into the published database

2.8.2 Processing the results

The results were exported from the Google Form to an Excel Spreadsheet held on the STFC project Sharepoint site. This was accessible to the entire team who were able to work in parallel on the following tasks:

- Anonymising responses
- Excluding some fields
- Mapping fields
- Summarising text responses
- Binning numerical responses
- Categorising responses
- Missing values

- Outlier checking
- Excluding records
- Correlation checking

The overall mapping of the input ("internal") database of responses to the public dataset is provided in [Appendix 2](#).

2.8.2.1 *Anonymising responses*

It was agreed that the responses should be anonymised in the public view of the report and database. The [rationale](#) for this decision is discussed below.

2.8.2.2 *Excluding some fields*

Some fields were excluded from the public dataset based on the following criteria:

- Irrelevant/metadata fields: such as the timestamp when the response was submitted
- The response identified an individual or the location of the facility (which would contradict the anonymised approach).

2.8.2.3 *Mapping fields*

Some fields were mapped to a more general response, for example:

- Location: mapped from a city/town to a region (for anonymisation)
- Total number of processing cores, or GPUs: mapped to two new columns, `n_cpus` and `n_gpus`.

2.8.2.4 *Summarising text responses*

In some text responses the respondent gave information that would identify the facility. We removed such information in the public dataset.

2.8.2.5 *Binning and categorising responses*

2.8.2.5.1 *Binning numerical responses*

In order to be able to visualise the spread of responses, it is useful to bin numerical responses into a set of discrete ranges. This was done for all numerical fields. As a first pass we aimed to use a linear scale but this was not appropriate in every case (i.e. where the range of responses was very large) and a non-linear scale was adopted when needed.

2.8.2.5.1.1 *Extract numbers from text*

Where a response includes text and numbers, the numerical value was extracted. Additionally, numerical responses were scaled to a consistent unit in cases where different respondents used different units (e.g. MB, GB, TB).

2.8.2.5.1.2 *Interpreting numeric values*

In some cases it was necessary to interpret a numerical value from text. We followed this a approach:

1. If a range of values was provided: we chose the central value
2. If the response was given as "less than X": we chose a value just below X

2.8.2.5.2 *Categorising responses*

In order to aid visualisation and analysis, most text responses were also mapped to a set of categories. We aimed to keep these to less than 10 in most cases.

2.8.2.6 Missing values

In the case of missing values (i.e. empty responses) – we left these blank. In some cases they were mapped to "No answer" or "N/A" in the mapped values.

2.8.2.7 Outlier checking

Summary statistics were calculated for each of the numerical responses to check for outliers. This enabled the team to identify questionable responses and to investigate them as required.

2.8.2.8 Excluding records

Despite the approach adopted for collecting DRI facility contacts, there were 7 responses that were excluded as not being relevant to the survey. These are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Records excluded from the results.

Record #	Reason for exclusion
Record 1	Test record
Record 3	A software and research collaboration rather than a facility. Most fields provided no content.
Record 8	European service, hosted outside UK and not UKRI funded.
Record 17	An executive agency of the UK Department of Health & Social Care. No actual facility listed.
Record 22	Facility is international, with only 10% UKRI involvement. Worth commenting on this as a case to capture in future where SMALL INVOLVEMENT IN BIG FACILITY might be relevant to overall UKRI picture.
Record 25	US-based facility with no UKRI funding.
Record 37	Recipient said survey should not have come to them as the facility is not part of the UKRI DRI.

2.8.2.9 Correlation checking

A correlation matrix was generated to provide a quick check of which fields might be correlated. This might identifier trends that are useful to look into in more detail.

2.8.3 Statistics

A Jupyter Notebook⁶ was generated written to analyse and visualise the data. This provided statistics reported below. The statistics were generated from looking at the overall spread of responses.

2.8.4 Individual responses

In some cases, individual responses included detailed reflections, opinions and ideas that the team think considered important to include. Where appropriate, these are highlighted in the results.

2.9 Identifying key findings

2.9.1 Context

The process of identifying the key findings is taken in the context of wider experience and discussions had by the team that undertook the DRI Mapping and case study tasks. Additionally, the team has been communicating with the sandpit project teams and other stakeholders in the project. Key findings are expected to be cross-referenceable with those identified in the wider project.

2.9.2 Extrapolation and correlation

It is important to stress that the findings of this work should be based on evidence. We are therefore guarded against extrapolating from results without caveats, and any potential correlations should be scrutinised before reaching conclusions of their representativeness.

⁶ https://github.com/net-zero-dri/dri-mapping-dataset/blob/main/example_notebook.ipynb

2.9.3 Potential interactions between responses

The ideal outcome of this work would allow meaningful questions to be asked of the database. In some cases these would make connections between different questions that were posed. Examples of this might be "is the PUE of facilities lower (i.e. are they more efficient) is you move further north?" and "which research councils appear to have the largest energy footprint?"

2.10 Publication and accessibility of results

2.10.1 "Internal" and "Public" data

Through the EAG interactions, it was agreed that the public dataset would only include anonymised information.

2.10.1.1 Rationale

The following reasons were made for pursuing an anonymised database approach:

1. The response level would be greater if the outputs were not public: because respondents would be less cautious about engaging
2. Some of the results may not be completely accurate and therefore could be misleading if viewed out of the context of the survey
3. The aim of this work is to understand what kind of information needs to be found out and shared. Future work is likely to include more information in the public domain.

2.10.2 Data Format

The "internal" database has managed as an Excel Spreadsheet which can be read directly into Python code for further checking and processing.

The public dataset will be provided a comma-separated-variables (CSV) file because that is considered the most accessible format for sharing and re-use.

2.10.3 Metadata and guidance

The public dataset is provided alongside the following metadata and guidance files:

1. Original full questionnaire
2. Mapping of the questionnaire questions to the public dataset columns
3. Long names for the database column names
4. Guidance on working with the dataset
 - a. Caveats
 - b. Disclaimer about the accuracy of the data
 - c. Examples of using the a Jupyter Notebook to analyse and visualise the data

2.10.4 Visualisation and analysis tools

There is a publicly available GitHub repository that includes an example Jupyter Notebook that can be used to generate statistics and visualisations from the public dataset. Instructions on how to access and run the Notebook are given here:

<https://github.com/net-zero-dri/dri-mapping-dataset/blob/main/README.md>

2.10.5 Publication location

The results are published on the public Zenodo repository here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7784877>

All relevant files and instructions are available from that link.

3 Results

This section details the results that were obtained from the survey. We start by looking at how many responses were received and then move on to analysing the numerical and statistical data.

Categorical data and free-text responses are then covered. Note that discussions about the results are saved for the [next section](#) of the document.

3.1 Response overview

The response counts are as follows:

- Contacted: 123
- Responded: 51
- Valid responses: 44 (after excluding 7)
- **Response rate: 51/123 = 41%**

3.2 Results by section

The results are presented as a series of charts, which have been grouped into the following sections (adapted from the original questionnaire structure):

1. Facility, funding and community
2. Physical characteristics
3. Energy supply
4. Energy usage and efficiency
5. Environmental policy and practice
6. User engagement and training

3.2.1 Results: Facility, funding and community

Summary points:

- There was a relatively good spread of responses across the research councils, but potential gaps were: AHRC, Innovate UK, MRC, Research England
- There was a mix of regions around the UK
- Most reported their primary function as HPC (42.5%) or "Other" (37.5%)
- Around ⅓ had at least 50% UKRI funding
- Over half of responses did not use the EPSRC "Tier" categorisation

3.2.2 Results: Physical characteristics

Summary points:

- The main physical components were: CPU (27.5%), Server – CPU & Disk (20.0%), GPU & CPU (17.5%)
- There was a range of server counts: 73.1% with less have 500 servers, 19.2% have 500-1000 servers and the rest have from 1000-5000 servers.
- Less than half of the responses reported their CPU count. Of those that did:
 - Over half have less than 10,000 CPUs
 - 39.1% have 10,000-100,000 CPUs
 - 8.7% have 100,000-1,000,000 CPUs
- Only 7 responded with GPU counts: the highest count was in the range 400-600.
- Over half have a storage capacity of over 1PB. The largest was in the range 100-200PB.

Main physical infrastructure (main_physical_comp)
[40 valid responses from 51]

Number of servers (n_server)
[34 valid responses from 51]

n_gpus
[7 valid responses from 51]

Number of CPUs (n_cpus)
[24 valid responses from 51]

Storage capacity (PBs) (storage)
[34 valid responses from 51]

3.2.3 Results: Energy supply

Summary points:

- Most facility managers did not know whether they were using green energy, or whether there was an option to purchase it from the current supplier.
- 23.5% were purchasing more than ¼ of their energy from renewable sources.
- Over 50% reported some on-site energy generation, such as on-premises solar. NOTE: the quantity of on-site generation was not recorded.
- Most systems were air-cooled. 7.7% re-use warm air (waste heat).
- The parent institution/organisation typically managed the electricity supply. In one case the energy contract is centrally negotiated between supplier(s) and collection of institutions.

Have control over choice of energy supply? (nrg_supply_ctrl)
[39 valid responses from 51]

Energy supplier has policy on low-carbon provision? (nrg_supply_pol)
[33 valid responses from 51]

Mix of renewable and non-renewables? (nrg_supply_mix)
[34 valid responses from 51]

On-site generation/storage of energy? (on_site_nrg)
[37 valid responses from 51]

Electricity purchased by (nrg_supply_purch)
[37 valid responses from 51]

Does cooling re-use warm air to heat other buildings? (heat_reuse)
[39 valid responses from 51]

Cooling system type (cool_sys)
[39 valid responses from 51]

3.2.4 Results: Energy usage and efficiency

Summary points:

- 30 responded with a value for the annual energy usage (MWh/yr). Only 10 gave a response for peak energy usage - which would not differ from annual energy usage if the system was fully utilised most of the time. Most responses consumed less than 5,000 MWh/yr. The highest usage was in the range 20,000-25,000 MWh/yr.
- Only 1 response reported that they could vary their energy consumption over time to be more energy efficient.
- Less than 10 record/provide efficiency metrics. Those that do are mainly using Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE).
- When calculating PUE, most reported a value < 1.4. Some were up to 2.4.
- There was some scepticism about the value of PUE – e.g. it can be misrepresentative.

Energy usage (MWh/yr) (nrg_use_mwh_yr)
[41 valid responses from 51]

Max Theoretical Energy usage (MWh/yr) (nrg_use_max_mwh_yr)
[18 valid responses from 51]

Can exploit energy consumption variation over time? (variation_nrg_use)
[37 valid responses from 51]

Efficiency metrics used (suggested_nrg_metric)
[33 valid responses from 51]

Power Usage Effectiveness [near 1 is best] (pue)
[17 valid responses from 51]

Opinion of PUE as efficiency metric? (effic_metrics)
[27 valid responses from 51]

- About 1/3 knew about their emissions in terms of the GHG emissions scopes:
 - One was already classed as Net Zero.
 - Some had done detailed assessments of their emissions.
 - Most has not done any assessment.

Proportions of GHG Emission Scopes (nrg_ghg_scopes)
 [35 valid responses from 51]
Don't know

3.2.5 Results: Environmental Policy and Practice

Summary points:

- Around ½ said that purchasing policy considers environmental factors.
- Around ½ said that disposal policy considers environmental factors.
- Over ¾ said that planning/design of facilities considers environmental factors.
- Over half do some form of energy usage monitoring. This happens at a range of levels, typically per rack/PDU. In some cases per server/node.
- A range of responses was received for estimating/measuring the proportional breakdown of energy consumption by type of component.
- Less than 20% said they would be able to manage the load to exploit low-carbon energy supply times.

Does environmental impact affect purchasing policy? (purchase_environ_consider) [34 valid responses from 51]

Does environmental impact affect disposal policy? (disposal_environ_consider) [34 valid responses from 51]

Is the environmental impact considered in planning/design of new facilities? (planned_environ_consider) [34 valid responses from 51]

Energy monitoring tools (nrg_monitor_tool) [38 valid responses from 51]

Proportions of energy consumed by each system component (detailed_nrg_cons_comp) [36 valid responses from 51]

Can manage the load to exploit low-carbon energy supply? (load_management) [35 valid responses from 51]

3.2.6 Results: User Engagement and Training

Summary points:

- There was a large range of user counts, from less than 100 up to 50,000.
- About ¼ said that they have information on the energy footprint of user behaviour.
- Only one respondent had a budget to include training on environmental impact.
- 25% said that some form of training was required before allowing users to use the facility – but not related to environmental impact.
- Over 70% said that standards, policies and certification are needed.

- There was little consensus on training needs for the facility team, with 11.1% identifying "Training on energy efficiency/environmental sustainability".
- The majority said that training does affect user behaviour.
- When asked what could be achieved with an unlimited budget, the top responses were:
 - Training users in optimisation/efficiency (18.5%)
 - New facility with optimised design/technology (11.1%)

Does training affect user behaviour? (training_impact)
[13 valid responses from 51]

With unlimited budget, how would you optimise efficiency? (imag_user_supp)
[33 valid responses from 51]

3.3 Free-text responses

There was a range of responses in terms of the number of questions answered and the level of detail provided. Table 2 highlights some of the interesting points that were raised in free-text responses.

We have recorded how many valid responses related to each point, and we also include a commentary in the final column which feeds into the discussion section.

Table 2. Free-text responses, their frequency and comments on their relevance.

Question (or "General" if raised in response to multiple questions)	Response(s) [paraphrased]	Number of responses that highlighted this issue	Commentary
General	Survey was long and involved significant data gathering from recipients. Some of the questions in the survey required quite a lot of work to get the information. It would have been nice to have been able to see all the questions in advance to gather the information needed, which includes asking other people (e.g., our building and facilities manager, our head of ITG).	~10 (estimated)	The survey asked for a lot of information, across a range of topics. This was a potential barrier to engagement.
General	[Our role is to help] UK businesses and organisations of any size to explore and adopt supercomputing, data science and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies.	1	Parts of the DRI that have a role in supporting use of technology could potentially <i>influence</i> other organisations running computing infrastructure (e.g. influence policies, conduct community engagement) outside of UKRI.
General	Financial cost leads purchasing decision at present.	1	Only 12 respondents gave an actual answer. It is likely that the larger facilities are more affected by environmental policy factors.
6.10 Do you consider that Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) is the most suitable measure of efficiency? ...	Reponses included: - PUE can be misleading - In short, no PUE is not a good measure of efficiency because it doesn't consider the efficiency of utilisation of what is being powered and cooled - No, as its value limited by the energy use of the underlying cooling system	6	PUE often mentioned as not the best metric but there is no clear better alternative at the moment.
8.2 Do you have a budget allocated to user training relating to environmental issues, energy usage and efficiency? ...	Would like to, but not aware of existing funding sources.	1	Availability of funding could act as an incentive for training programmes.
8.3 Do you think the training has a noticeable impact on user behaviour?	One response cited evidence of user behaviour changes in response to our providing information about their kWhr usage and carbon footprint: (1) a PI who noticed that two of his students were nominally doing the same calculations using different codes but had very different kWhr reports; (2) a PhD student asked whether a particular simulation should be continued, as they weren't sure how long it would take but it had already generated sufficient carbon to 'power my house for 300 years!' [We] ran a pilot where users are sent the carbon and energy footprints of their jobs on a monthly basis.	1	This supports the notion that giving information to users, and supervisors, helps to empower their decision-making and behaviour.

	Pls get a monthly e-mail showing the footprints of their project broken down by user. Individual users get a monthly e-mail detailing the footprints of the jobs they have submitted.		
8.4 Do you have information on users' energy footprints?	One response highlighted that there are genuine concerns for users, citing experience of some researchers trying to corner / shame / belittle colleagues whose research has a large footprint.	1	This response highlights a potential danger in reporting/publicising the energy/carbon cost of specific research . Whilst this was only one response it should be noted as an area of sensitivity that needs to be addressed fairly and carefully.
9.3 Do you think there is a need for standards, policies and/or certification to make progress towards Net Zero?	<p>It would help if vendors provided CO2e figures for manufacture and shipping in a clear (itemized per component, actual figures not graph), consistent (same data, calcs and breakdown from each vendor) and transparent way (i.e. tell me what is included, and any assumptions made in the calculation).</p> <p>Most vendors seem to use PAIA⁷ to calculate carbon footprint. However, the data is often not straightforward to interpret.</p> <p>If UKRI are going to use absolute emissions or carbon intensity as a factor in funding decisions, then we need transparent and fair comparisons across vendors/cloud providers/HPC centres, and that will be really complicated to do well. And probably fairly easy to greenwash.</p>	1	These points highlight the need for standards in reporting the carbon footprint of all parts of the supply chain. They also stress how engagement with providers is key to ensure that the data is relevant/valid.
General	Would a site visit to review the facility be more effective? Some questions are wider in scope than others.	1	For larger facilities, it may be quicker and more useful to have one-to-one meetings and/or a site visit.

⁷ PAIA: <https://msl.mit.edu/projects/paia/main.html>

3.4 Correlations

In order to look at possible correlations between different answers, a correlation matrix was calculated (see figure 2) that presents the correlation coefficient (R) between any pair of numerical responses. This excluded any columns in which there were less than 10 valid responses as we considered that a minimum threshold for investigating correlations.

Figure 2. Correlation matrix between numerical responses.

The main correlations were between features that are already known to be well correlated, these include:

- The number of CPUs
- The number of servers
- The overall energy usage

The relationship between the annual energy usage (MWh/yr) and the PUE is shown in figure 3. The R-value for the correlation is -0.33. This is a relatively low negative correlation which reflects the expected result that larger facilities are likely to be more efficient.

Figure 3. Scatter plot of PUE versus Annual Energy Usage (MWh/yr).

Additionally, the following correlation coefficients were investigated:

- Approximate latitude VS whether the facility could adapt its usage to local weather conditions:
 - This showed no significant correlation within the dataset (R-value: 0.005)
- Approximate latitude VS PUE value:
 - This showed no significant correlation within the dataset (R-value: 0.08)

4 Discussion and Recommendations

This section provides a discussion of what we learnt from the process of attempting to map the DRI. Key findings (KFs) and recommendations (RECs) are numbered and included in text boxes. The discussion examines community engagement and the main themes arising from the results.

4.1 Engaging the community

Community engagement could be considered as an essential aspect of the overarching UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project. In terms of the DRI Mapping process, there are three main components:

1. Identifying the community (and the DRI itself)
2. Collecting information
3. Developing the community (through contacts)

4.1.1 Identifying the community (and the DRI itself)

The DRI is not a clearly defined entity. It is made up of a range of resources, people, etc. The physical components of the DRI can be considered as the computing facilities, which range from large HPC sites to each individual device. From our discussions with UKRI staff, there is not a definitive list or database of the DRI.

In this project, we started with the UKRI InfraPortal website as a database of resources that would constitute the DRI. However, there InfraPortal has largely been populated on a voluntary basis so it is not comprehensive. From a subset of the InfraPortal contacts (using the criteria specified in [section 2.3](#)), we gathered 109 contacts. We extended our list to 123 facilities by including additional DRIs identified by the network of contacts made in the project.

KF 1	The physical DRI varies from large-scale facility down to individual devices. A consistent and reliable estimate of the entire DRI is required in order to capture the state of the system and to measure changes over time.
REC 1	Create a consistent and reliable estimate of the physical DRI. This might be generated from a system-wide survey and/or a model based on sampling example facilities.

4.1.2 Collecting information

Whilst the response rate to the survey (51 out of 123 [41%]) was a reasonable return, many questions were left unanswered or were answered with "Don't know", "No" or "N/A". From the responses, and direct communication with some respondents, it was clear that:

- The survey was long (many questions).
- The recipient often had no access to the information requested, or they would need to request it from other people/systems.
- Gathering the information was a time-consuming manual process.
- Some recipients were sceptical about the value/outcomes from providing the information.
- For some smaller facilities, many of the questions were not relevant.

KF 2	The DRI consists of a broad range of systems that vary greatly in scale and purpose. The level of detail required about each component should vary based on size and environmental footprint.
REC 2	<p>Future engagement with DRI contacts should take into account the relative size and impact of different facilities. The amount of detail required from each component of the DRI should be proportional to the potential impact of making policy and system changes.</p> <p>NOTE: This process should be managed carefully to avoid missing opportunities where a change to a relatively small system could be significant if applied across the DRI (e.g. a change to <i>all</i> UKRI laptops).</p>

4.1.3 Developing the community (through contacts)

Without a clear picture of the overall size of the DRI, we cannot make definitive statements about the coverage attained by the survey. Equally, there is uncertainty around the quantitative data and not enough data points to investigate correlations. Although many responses were sparse in terms of the amount of information captured, some responses provided a wealth of detailed information. The detail typically came from contacts who:

- Were already engaged with the overall scoping project.
- Were highly motivated in terms of environmental sustainability.
- Already had access to much of the information because of their specific circumstances/reporting/research.

KF 3	There are some contacts in the UKRI DRI community that already have (i) the ability to collect and share a significant of information related to their energy/carbon usage, and (ii) are keen to engage with the Net Zero agenda.
REC 3.1	Work with the contacts made within the DRI Mapping process to explore the most effective ways of maintaining and evolving community engagement to build the DRI database required in future.
REC 3.2	<p>Consider incentives for improving engagement, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding mechanisms for early adopters • Community champions – to reach out via their own networks • Support (i.e. tools/best practice advice/training) for early adopters • Introduce a voluntary reporting system, such as that provided by the Laboratory Environmental Assessment Framework (LEAF⁸)

4.2 Main themes of the results

This section presents the key findings and recommendations generated from analysing the results in section 3.

KF 4	There was a relatively good spread of responses across the research councils, but potential gaps were: AHRC, Innovate UK, MRC, Research England.
REC 4	Contact should be made with each Research Council to ensure that the main DRI footprint of each is appropriately captured in a future DRI database.

⁸ <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/sustainable/leaf-laboratory-efficiency-assessment-framework>

KF 5	The variety of different DRI facilities means that it is hard to compare like-with-like.
REC 5	Building on the results here, a set of categories should be defined to describe different types of DRI facility. A specific set of metrics and information should be agreed to in relation to each facility type.

KF 6	Most facility managers did not know whether they were using green energy, or whether there was an option to purchase it from the current supplier. Of those that were purchasing green energy, more than 75% of their energy comes from renewable sources. In some cases, institutions had formed a consortium in order to negotiate with energy suppliers.
REC 6	Some parts of the community have demonstrated that purchasing renewable energy can be combined with financial and scientific success. UKRI should consider a policy of purchasing electricity from renewable sources across the entire DRI. NOTES: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience and knowledge should be shared in relation to on-site renewable energy generation. • Facility managers should be invited into the energy purchase discussions to improve the connection between high-level policies and practices at the facility level

KF 7	7.7% of respondents said that they re-use warm air (waste heat) to heat other buildings.
REC 7	Engage with respondents that have heat re-use systems in place. Look for opportunities for knowledge exchange to make heat re-use into standard practice for UKRI.

KF 8	Sharing of the annual energy usage (MWh/yr) is a high-level quantity that can be usefully compared across all facilities (and with other sectors).
REC 8	The initial design for a database of DRI facilities should include annual energy usage.

KF 9	Less than 23% of respondents record efficiency metrics. Those that do are mainly using Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), but there was scepticism about the utility of PUE. Over 70% said that standards, policies and certification are needed in this area.
REC 9	Agree standard metrics for recording and sharing efficiency and energy usage information. These metrics need to be developed in conjunction with appropriate tooling and hardware/software specifications that are accessible to all system managers.

	These standards should incorporate the GHG Protocol Emission Scopes.
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KF 10	Some respondents reported significant advances in terms of policies that consider environmental impact.
REC 10	Provide a service, such as a centralised hub/group/knowledge-base, to gather best practice and share the outcomes/impacts of positive changes.

KF 11	A variety of energy usage monitoring currently takes place, at a range of levels (such as monitoring of each individual job, compute node, entire rack, or Power Distribution Unit (PDU)).
REC 11	Provide guidance and support for facility managers to enable them to develop and deploy systems for monitoring and reporting energy usage.

KF 12	Only ~25% of facilities had information on the energy footprint of users. But there was a consensus that training has an impact on user behaviour. Additionally, a facility gave evidence that reporting usage information to users and PIs has an impact on usage behaviour.
REC 12	Develop a fair approach for recording, monitoring and reporting energy usage information at appropriate levels (e.g. per job, per user, per group, per research theme). NOTE: It was pointed out that there may be unforeseen negative consequences of making energy usage information public (or within institution) – it could be used to <i>shame</i> a high-energy user. A solution must be carefully managed to avoid such outcomes.

KF 13	Only 1 respondent (out of 44) had a budget to include training on environmental impact. 25% said that some form of training was required before allowing users to use the facility – but not related to environmental impact. The majority said that training does affect user behaviour. Training users and managers in efficiency/sustainable were identified as important.
REC 13	Information, support and training is essential to bring about the change required to meet the Net Zero target. This needs to be made a funding and resourcing priority so that: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The knowledge and human resources exist to provide the information/training. 2. The need to undertake training on sustainability issues (such as "green software engineering") is a funded and supported activity across all levels including decision-makers, PIs, system managers and end-users.

KF 14	There is a great deal of "good will" towards changing behaviour and policy in order to achieve the UKRI Net Zero target. There is also a common theme that people are stretched and are being focussed on, and measured against, other targets.
REC 14	Net Zero needs to become an explicit and significant concern of every single DRI user and stakeholder. A system of recognition, acknowledgement and reward is required to incentivise and encourage positive action on sustainability from all staff and users.

KF 15	An ongoing effort is required to record change/progress over time.
REC 15	A public database of key information about the UKRI DRI should be collected and updated routinely. Where possible, automated data feeds should be used to improve the data coverage and quality.

KF 16	Investigating the correlation between PUE vs overall energy usage showed a negative correlation. This requires a larger, more robust, data coverage but we would expect a trend of bigger facilities being more efficient.
REC 16	Gather a comprehensive dataset on the efficiency of facilities compared with their overall energy usage (e.g. their size). If there is a significant correlation: investigate options for moving more processing into centralised services to achieve higher overall efficiency.

KF 17	One large international facility was excluded from the analysis because it only included a 10% UKRI funded share.
REC 17	Future information gathering regarding the carbon-footprint of UKRI-funded resources should ensure that some large facilities are not ignored because UKRI only funds a minority share. If they are significant in size, then this should be captured in a comprehensive future database.

4.3 Gaps in the DRI Mapping process

4.3.1 Personal compute: the laptops and desktop machines used as client hardware to access the main DRI facilities.

Personal compute is not captured within the work described in this report. A more detailed audit or analysis will be required to understand what percentage of the overall UKRI DRI relates to personal devices such as desktop machines, laptops, tablets and phones.

REC 18	A detailed audit or analysis should be undertaken to understand what percentage of the overall UKRI DRI relates to personal devices such as desktop machines, laptops, tablets and phones.
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4.3.2 The UK academic network: The Janet research and education network that underpins communication and data transfer between nodes of the UKRI DRI.

The academic network infrastructure (i.e. Janet) is not accounted for within this work. Whilst we do not expect it to be comparable with the main computing and storage infrastructure, it is important to understand its contribution to the overall carbon footprint of the DRI.

REC 19	Carry out an assessment of the percentage contribution of the academic network to the overall carbon footprint of the DRI. If it is significant, then investigate how that footprint could be reduced.
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4.3.3 Cloud compute

The amount of UKRI science that is taking place on the "public cloud" (such as Google Cloud, Amazon EC2 and Microsoft Azure) is unknown, but is likely to grow in the next 5 years. It is important to understand how significant this is when compared to UKRI-owned and majority-funded facilities.

REC 20	Carry out an assessment of the percentage contribution of the use of the public cloud to the overall carbon footprint of the DRI. Consider whether there might be environmental advantages of using the cloud for certain use cases.
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4.4 Summary of recommendations

The following table includes all recommendations in a single table, in the format required by the core project reporting. An additional column has been added to group them by the following broad categories:

- Defining the DRI
- Engaging the community
- Disseminating knowledge and best practice
- Creating a database of DRI information
- Innovating and supporting the community
- Net Zero policy and strategy
- Undertaking further research

Broad category	Recommendation title	Statement	Reasoning	Risks	What DRI Topic	Key words	Action Timescale	Applicable Tiers	Relevant links
	A short title name	Main statement of recommendation	Reasoning behind recommendation and summary of evidence	Any risks associated with this recommendation		Type in key words with commas in between			Insert links to relevant papers, findings etc
Define the DRI	Define the physical DRI	Create a consistent and reliable estimate of the physical DRI. This might be generated from a system-wide survey and/or a model based on sampling example facilities.	The physical DRI varies from large-scale facility down to individual devices. A consistent and reliable estimate of the entire DRI is required in order to capture the state of the system and to measure changes over time.	- Too much effort focused on capturing everything - Definition of the DRI misses key areas (addressed in other recommendations below)	Architecture	DRI, facilities, physical, hardware, database	Now-ish	4	
Engage the community	The level of accounting and engagement should match the size and impact of each DRI component	Future engagement with DRI contacts should take into account the relative size and impact of different facilities. The amount of detail required from each component of the DRI should be proportional to the potential impact of making policy and system changes. NOTE: This process should be managed carefully to avoid missing opportunities where a change to a relatively small system could be significant if applied across the DRI (e.g. a change to <i>all</i> UKRI laptops).	The DRI consists of a broad range of systems that vary greatly in scale and purpose. The level of detail required about each component should vary based on size and environmental footprint.	- Approach needs to be balanced and fair – capable of incorporating a variety of DRI components/types.	Architecture	DRI, facilities, physical, hardware, database	Now-ish	4	
Engage the community	Engage with interesting parties and incentivise	Work with the contacts made within the DRI Mapping process to explore the most effective	There are some contacts in the UKRI DRI community that already have (i) the	- Need to ensure that the approach will generalise to	Behaviour change	DRI, facilities, community	Now-ish	4	

	early engagement	ways of maintaining and evolving community engagement to build the DRI database required in future. Consider incentives for improving engagement, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding mechanisms for early adopters • Community champions – to reach out via their own networks • Support (i.e. tools/best practice advice/training) for early adopters • Introduce a voluntary reporting system, such as that provided by the Laboratory Environmental Assessment Framework (LEAF) 	ability to collect and share a significant of information related to their energy/carbon usage, and (ii) are keen to engage with the Net Zero agenda.	all cases; avoid narrow view based on specific participants.		engagement			
Engage the community	Engage with all Research Councils	Contact should be made with each Research Council to ensure that the main DRI footprint of each is appropriately captured in a future DRI database.	There was a relatively good spread of responses across the research councils, but potential gaps were: AHRC, Innovate UK, MRC, Research England.	- Specific Research Councils are better represented because they engage more.	Behaviour change	DRI, facilities, community engagement	Now-ish	4	
Define the DRI	Categorise the DRI facilities by a defined set of metrics	Building on the results here, a set of categories should be defined to describe different types of DRI facility. A specific set of metrics and information should be agreed to in relation to each facility type.	The variety of different DRI facilities means that it is hard to compare like-with-like.	- Categories are too broad, or too narrow	Architecture	DRI, monitor, metrics, categorisation	Now-ish	4	
Disseminate knowledge and best practice	Share knowledge and experience of green energy adoption within the community	Some parts of the community have demonstrated that purchasing renewable energy can be combined with financial and scientific success. UKRI should consider a policy of purchasing electricity from renewable sources across the entire DRI. NOTES: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience and knowledge should be shared in relation to on-site renewable energy generation. • Facility managers should be invited into the energy purchase discussions to improve the connection between high-level 	Most facility managers did not know whether they were using green energy, or whether there was an option to purchase it from the current supplier. Of those that were purchasing green energy, more than 75% of their energy comes from renewable sources. In some cases, institutions had formed a consortium in order to negotiate with energy suppliers.	- Comparisons of energy supply/usage are not made fairly across the DRI; need to include all factors that have an impact.	Electricity Supply	DRI, energy supply, renewables, green energy, purchasing policy	Within 5 years	4	

		policies and practices at the facility level							
Disseminate knowledge and best practice	Share knowledge and experience of heat re-use in data centres	Engage with respondents that have heat re-use systems in place. Look for opportunities for knowledge exchange to make heat re-use into standard practice for UKRI.	7.7% of respondents said that they re-use warm air (waste heat) to heat other buildings.		Rebound and Efficiency	DRI, energy efficiency, heat reuse, cooling	Within 5 years	4	
Create a database of DRI information	Use "annual energy usage" as fundamental measure in DRI database	The initial design for a database of DRI facilities should include annual energy usage.	Sharing of the annual energy usage (MWh/yr) is a high-level quantity that can be usefully compared across all facilities (and with other sectors).	- Annual energy usage should not be interpreted in isolation. Factors such as "scientific throughput" and efficiency are also key.	Carbon emissions	DRI, energy usage	Now-ish	4	
Create a database of DRI information	Create standards for recording and reporting energy usage and efficiency	Agree standard metrics for recording and sharing efficiency and energy usage information. These metrics need to be developed in conjunction with appropriate tooling and hardware/software specifications that are accessible to all system managers. These standards should incorporate the GHG Protocol Emission Scopes.	Less than 23% of respondents record efficiency metrics. Those that do are mainly using Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), but there was scepticism about the utility of PUE. Over 70% said that standards, policies and certification are needed in this area.	- The standards need to be realistic, achievable and applicable to a wide range of systems	Other: Standards	DRI, energy usage, efficiency, metrics, reporting, standards	Within 5 years	4	
Disseminate knowledge and best practice	Create a centralised resource to gather best practice and promote positive change	Provide a service, such as a centralised hub/group/knowledge-base, to gather best practice and share the outcomes/impacts of positive changes.	Some respondents reported significant advances in terms of policies that consider environmental impact.	- Centralised resource should be on openness, evidence-based information and technical/organisational/societal diversity – in order to ensure that it avoids bias or short-term thinking	Behaviour change	DRI, knowledge base, hub, best practice, information sharing, positive change	Within 5 years	4	
Innovation and support	Support facility managers in monitoring and reporting energy metrics	Provide guidance and support for facility managers to enable them to develop and deploy systems for monitoring and reporting energy usage.	A variety of energy usage monitoring currently takes place, at a range of levels (such as monitoring of each individual job, compute node, entire rack, or Power Distribution Unit (PDU)).	- Tools and systems are not general enough – need to ensure that suppliers are engaged in the process	Technology	DRI, energy usage, efficiency, metrics, reporting, standards, training, facility manager	Within 5 years	4	
Innovation and support	Develop a fair system for capturing energy usage at multiple levels.	Develop a fair approach for recording, monitoring and reporting energy usage information at appropriate levels (e.g. per job, per user, per group, per research theme).	Only ~25% of facilities had information on the energy footprint of users. But there was a consensus that training has an impact on user behaviour. Additionally, a facility gave evidence that reporting usage	- System could have negative effects of inhibiting good science because of perceived threat of negative attention for	Behaviour change	DRI, energy usage, efficiency, metrics, reporting, user, job, feedback	Within 5 years	4	

		NOTE: It was pointed out that there may be unforeseen negative consequences of making energy usage information public (or within institution) – it could be used to <i>shame</i> a high-energy user. A solution must be carefully managed to avoid such outcomes.	information to users and Pls has an impact on usage behaviour.	users with high energy usage.					
Disseminate knowledge and best practice	Resource Net Zero and sustainability training	Information, support and training is essential to bring about the change required to meet the Net Zero target. This needs to be made a funding and resourcing priority so that: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The knowledge and human resources exist to provide the information/training The need to undertake training on sustainability issues (such as "green software engineering") is a funded and supported activity across all levels including decision-makers, Pls, system managers and end-users. 	Only 1 respondent (out of 44) had a budget to include training on environmental impact. 25% said that some form of training was required before allowing users to use the facility – but not related to environmental impact. The majority said that training does affect user behaviour. Training users and managers in efficiency/sustainable were identified as important.	- over-emphasis on the negative impacts could make trainees feel powerless - need to find ways to demonstrate changing behaviour can have real impacts.	Behaviour change	Net Zero, sustainability, training, resourcing, impact	Within 5 years	4	
Net Zero policy and strategy	Embed Net Zero in all layers of UKRI	Net Zero needs to become an explicit and significant concern of every single DRI user and stakeholder. A system of recognition, acknowledgement and reward is required to incentivise and encourage positive action on sustainability from all staff and users.	There is a great deal of "good will" towards changing behaviour and policy in order to achieve the UKRI Net Zero target. There is also a common theme that people are stretched and are being focussed on, and measured against, other targets.	- Needs to be managed in a way that does not appear to be a top-down approach; Tapping into grass-roots activities helps to motivate and connect the community.	Behaviour change	Net Zero, strategy, sustainability, training, resourcing, impact	Within 5 years	4	
Create a database of DRI information	Create a public database of DRI information that is updated regularly	A public database of key information about the UKRI DRI should be collected and updated routinely. Where possible, automated data feeds should be used to improve the data coverage and quality.	An ongoing effort is required to record change/progress over time.	- Overly complex technological fixes may get in the way of real progress; need to take a pragmatic view on priorities.	Architecture	DRI, facilities, database, updates, change over time	Now-ish	4	
Innovation and support	Examine economies of scale: should more compute be centralised?	Gather a comprehensive dataset on the efficiency of facilities compared with their overall energy usage (e.g. their size). If there is a significant correlation: investigate options for moving more processing	Investigating the correlation between PUE vs overall energy usage showed a negative correlation. This requires a larger, more robust, data coverage but we	- Need a fair system to compare different systems that avoids assumptions	Procurement	DRI, facilities, energy usage, efficiency, scale	Now-ish	4	

		into centralised services to achieve higher overall efficiency.	would expect a trend of bigger facilities being more efficient.	and biases in the analysis.					
Define the DRI	Ensure partially UKRI-funded resources are appropriately captured	Future information gathering regarding the carbon-footprint of UKRI-funded resources should ensure that some large facilities are not ignored because UKRI only funds a minority share. If they are significant in size, then this should be captured in a comprehensive future database.	One large international facility was excluded from the analysis because it only included a 10% UKRI funded share.		Carbon emissions	DRI, facilities, energy usage, efficiency, minority share	Within 5 years	4	
Further research	Analyse the contribution and impact of personal devices within the DRI	A detailed audit or analysis should be undertaken to understand what percentage of the overall UKRI DRI relates to personal devices such as desktop machines, laptops, tablets and phones.	Personal compute is not captured within the work described in this report. A more detailed audit or analysis will be required to understand what percentage of the overall UKRI DRI relates to personal devices such as desktop machines, laptops, tablets and phones.	- Need to be aware of potential resistance in the community in terms of monitoring/controlting their use of personal devices. Needs to be managed in a way that gets buy-in from staff/researchers.	Carbon emissions	DRI, personal devices, individual, phone, tablet, desktop, laptop, energy usage, efficiency	Now-ish	4	
Further research	Analyse the contribution and impact of digital networks within the DRI	Carry out an assessment of the percentage contribution of the academic network to the overall carbon footprint of the DRI. If it is significant, then investigate how that footprint could be reduced.	The academic network infrastructure (i.e. Janet) is not accounted for within this work. Whilst we do not expect it to be comparable with the main computing and storage infrastructure, it is important to understand its contribution to the overall carbon footprint of the DRI.		Carbon emissions	DRI, network, bandwidth, interconnect, routing, energy usage, efficiency	Now-ish	4	
Further research	Analyse the contribution and impact of public cloud computing within the DRI	Carry out an assessment of the percentage contribution of the use of the public cloud to the overall carbon footprint of the DRI. Consider whether there might be environmental advantages of using the cloud for certain use cases.	The amount of UKRI science that is taking place on the "public cloud" (such as Google Cloud, Amazon EC2 and Microsoft Azure) is unknown, but is likely to grow in the next 5 years. It is important to understand how significant this is when compared to UKRI-owned and majority-funded facilities.	- Need to ensure that the system for accounting the carbon footprint of different public cloud services is fair and appropriate.	Carbon emissions	DRI, cloud computing, public cloud, Amazon Web Services, AWS, Google Cloud Platform, Microsoft Azure, energy usage, efficiency	Now-ish	4	

5 Conclusions

Mapping the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure has been shown to be a complex and involved task. There is no clear delineation of what the DRI is, and there is great variety in terms of the size, purpose, function and usage of the components of the DRI. Whilst some major parts of the DRI are already engaged with the Net Zero agenda, others are lacking information and training to be able to assess their carbon footprint.

The work outlined in this report demonstrates a pathfinder process that is essential for UKRI to accurately monitor and improve its energy usage and progress towards the Net Zero target. The generation of a list of the significant DRI Facilities is a pre-requisite to capturing the current situation. Furthermore, establishing a methodology for measuring or modelling the long tail of small facilities and personal compute is also required.

Within the constraints of this project, greater effort and resource should be directed at engaging with the community and gathering information from them. Various approaches might help to achieve this, but the most compelling is that Net Zero action should become recognised and rewarded at all levels of UKRI work.

The results and inferences within this work highlight the value of collecting and sharing information about the DRI to draw out best practice and opportunities for knowledge-exchange. Building a more comprehensive database of this information, and capturing temporal updates, will be essential for UKRI to reach Net Zero by 2040.

6 Appendices

6.1 Appendix 1: Full questionnaire

Section #	Form section	Question/Input	Answer type	Multiple or single choice options
1	Contact and facility info	Your full name	short free text	
1	Contact and facility info	Your email address	short free text	
1	Contact and facility info	Your job title	short free text	
1	Contact and facility info	Organisation/Institution	short free text	
1	Contact and facility info	Full name of the facility	short free text	
1	Contact and facility info	Short name or abbreviation for the facility (if appropriate)	short free text	
1	Contact and facility info	Website/URL for the facility (if appropriate)	short free text	
1	Contact and facility info	Based on the EPSRC "Tier" categorisation of facilities, how would you describe your facility? [See: https://www.ukri.org/councils/epsrc/facilities-and-resources/find-an-epsrc-facility-or-resource/]	multiple choice	- Tier 1 - Tier 2 - Tier 3 - Not categorisable by Tier
1	Contact and facility info	Location - e.g. town, city or county	short free text	
1	Contact and facility info	How many staff (FTEs) are employed in operating the facility?	numeric + short free text	
2	Funding and community	Which Research Councils (or other bodies) fund your facility?	multiple choice + short free text	- AHRC - BBSRC - ESRC - EPSRC - Innovate UK - MRC - NERC - Research England - STFC - Non-UKRI funding (please give details)
2	Funding and community	Do you know the percentage UKRI stake in the facility? Please state if known. (This would be 100% for all UKRI-owned or UKRI fully-funded facilities).	Y/N + numeric	
2	Funding and community	Do you know how many individual users your facility has per year? Please state if known	Y/N + numeric	
2	Funding and community	How would you define the geographical scope of your user community?	multiple choice	- International - National - Regional - Local
3	General characteristics	Does your facility support general purpose usage or a specific scientific focus? Please provide the specific focus if relevant.	multiple choice, and free text field.	- General Purpose - Specific scientific focus
3	General characteristics	If known, please characterise briefly the range of user activities carried out on the facility.	long free text	

3	General characteristics	How would you describe your facility in terms of its primary function?	multiple choice, with free text option	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High Performance Computing - High Throughput Computing - Cloud Computing - Storage (disk - traditional) - Storage (disk - object store) - Storage (tape) - Other (please specify)
3	General characteristics	What is the predominant component of physical infrastructure in your facility?	multiple choice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Server (CPU) - Server (GPU + CPU) - Server (CPU + Disk) - Disk (Magnetic) - Disk (SSD) - Tape - Other (please specify)
3	General characteristics	Is it straightforward to summarise information about the predominant server/processor types (manufacturer, specification etc.)? If so, please provide details. If not, please provide comments on why it is challenging to summarise this information.	Y/N + long free text	
4	Technical details	What type of cooling system do you use?	multiple choice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Air cooled - Liquid cooled - Hybrid - Other
4	Technical details	Does the cooling system re-use warm air to heat other buildings?	multiple choice	
4	Technical details	What is the total number of processing cores, or GPUs (if the main type), in your facility?	numeric	
4	Technical details	What is the total number of servers in your facility? (By "server", we typically mean each unit in a rack).	numeric	
4	Technical details	What is the total number of disks in your facility?	numeric	
4	Technical details	What is the current total storage capacity of your facility (in Petabytes)?	numeric	
4	Technical details	Do you have an estimate of the overall bandwidth utilisation between your facility and the rest of the world (in PB/year)?	numeric	
5	Energy supply	Do you have any direct control over your choice of energy supply?	Y/N + short free text	
5	Energy supply	Do you know the mix of renewable and non-renewable sources in your energy supply? If so, what percentage of your electricity is purchased on a green (renewable) tariff?	Y/N + numeric	
5	Energy supply	Who purchases electricity on behalf of the facility?	short free text	
5	Energy supply	Does your energy supplier have a policy on the provision of low-carbon energy? Please provide details.	Y/N/Don't know	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - No - Don't know

5	Energy supply	Do you make use of on-site generation/storage of energy? (Not including any research on energy storage that might be conducted) If so, please provide details.	Y/N + long free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	What energy monitoring tools do you have at your disposal?	short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	Please provide an estimate of your annual energy consumption in kWh.	numeric + short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	If your estimate of annual energy consumption is significantly different from the maximum annual energy draw, please also provide the latter. If we have both numbers, we can estimate how much of the time the facility is running near the theoretical "peak usage".	numeric + short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	At what level of granularity are you able to measure power consumption? (E.g. building, room, rack, server, processor, etc.)	short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	Do you know what proportion of the energy usage of the facility sits within each of the GHG emission scopes (1, 2 and 3)? [See: https://www.carbontrust.com/resources/briefing-what-are-scope-3-emissions] Please provide details.	Y/N + short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	Are you able to take advantage of the variation in energy consumption over time (days or weeks)? Please give details.	Y/N + short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	Can load be managed to maximise the use of low-carbon energy supply?	Y/N + short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	Do you record/provide any efficiency metrics for your energy usage? If so, please provide details.	Y/N + short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	Do you calculate the Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) for your facility? If so, what is the estimated annual value.	Y/N + short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency		short free text	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	Do you have knowledge about the proportions of energy consumption related to each component (e.g., storage, compute, networking, cooling etc.)? If so, please provide details, including whether the consumption is measured or based on information provided by manufacturers etc.,.	Y/N + numeric	
6	Energy usage and efficiency	Are there parts of your provision/service that are likely to register dramatic improvements in energy efficiency in the near future? Please provide details of what they are and what changes you anticipate.	long free text	
7	Environmental considerations and constraints	Does local weather have an impact on your need for cooling? If so, how significant is this in terms of energy usage.	Y/N + short free text	
7	Environmental considerations and constraints	Are there coal-peaking power plants in the area where your energy supplier is located?	Y/N/Don't know	- Yes - No - Don't know
7	Environmental considerations and constraints	Do you take environmental considerations into account when planning and designing a new facility? If so, please provide details.	Y/N + long free text	

7	Environmental considerations and constraints	Does your purchasing policy take into account environmental considerations? If so, please provide details.	Y/N + long free text	
7	Environmental considerations and constraints	Does your disposal policy take into account environmental considerations? If so, please provide details.	Y/N + long free text	
7	Environmental considerations and constraints	Please comment on whether there is any attempt to take into account the wider carbon footprint beyond that of operating the facility itself, for example due to manufacture, installation, disposal, or in terms of the three emissions scopes. [See: https://www.carbontrust.com/resources/briefing-what-are-scope-3-emissions]	long free text	
8	User engagement	Do you require users to meet a minimum knowledge level before using your facility? Please provide details, including whether knowledge of environmental factors is included.	Y/N + long free text	
8	User engagement	Do you have a budget allocated to user training relating to environmental issues, energy usage and efficiency? If so, how much (in total and per user)?	Y/N + numeric	
8	User engagement	Do you think the training has a noticeable impact on user behaviour? If so, in what way? Please provide details.	Y/N + short free text	
8	User engagement	Do you have information on users' energy footprints? If so, do you provide that information to your users? Please provide details.	Y/N + short free text	
8	User engagement	If you had an unlimited budget, what would you do to help users optimise the use of your facility in terms of energy efficiency? Please provide details.	long free text	

9	Other information, opportunity for feedback, and conclusion	Do you have any way of assessing "scientific throughput", i.e. the quantity and quality of scientific results obtained from work on your facility, and specifically relating it to facility usage (for example, research publications arising from a particular assignment of resources)? Please provide details.	long free text	
9	Other information, opportunity for feedback, and conclusion	What are the training needs for you and your team in terms of making progress towards Net Zero? Please provide details.	long free text	
9	Other information, opportunity for feedback, and conclusion	Do you think there is a need for standards, policies and/or certification to make progress towards Net Zero? Please provide details.	long free text	

9	Other information, opportunity for feedback, and conclusion	Are there any questions you would have expected us to ask but we did not, or any other information you think is relevant? Please provide details.	long free text	
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6.2 Appendix 2: Mapping of the initial question fields to fields provided in the public dataset.

Descriptive name (for documentation)	Column name (in public dataset)	Original survey question
Record number	record_no	N/A
Tier Category	tier_cat	1.8 Based on the EPSRC "Tier" categorisation of facilities, how would you describe your facility?
UK Region	region	1.9 Location (e.g. town, city or county)
Research Council funding	main_rcs	2.1.a Which are the main Research Councils (or other bodies) that fund your facility?
UKRI stake in the facility (as %)	ukri_pc	2.2 Do you know the percentage UKRI stake in the facility? Please state if known. (This would be 100% for all UKRI-owned or UKRI fully-funded facilities).
Number of users	n_users	2.3 Do you know how many individual users your facility has per year? Please state if known.
Broad purpose	purpose	3.1.a Does your facility support general-purpose usage or a specific scientific focus?
Primary function of facility	primary_func_facility	3.3.a How would you describe your facility in terms of its primary function?
Main physical infrastructure	main_physical_comp	3.4.a What is the predominant component of physical infrastructure in your facility?
Cooling system type	cool_sys	4.1.a What type of cooling system do you use?
Does cooling re-use warm air to heat other buildings?	heat_reuse	4.2 Does the cooling system re-use warm air to heat other buildings?
Number of CPUs	n_cpus	4.3a What is the total number of processing cores, or GPUs (if the main type), in your facility? [Interpreted as CPUs]
Number of GPUs	n_gpus	4.3b What is the total number of processing cores, or GPUs (if the main type), in your facility? [Interpreted as GPUs]
Number of servers	n_server	4.4 What is the total number of physical servers in your facility? (By "server", we typically mean each unit in a rack).
Storage capacity (PBs)	storage	4.5 What is the current total storage capacity of your facility in Petabytes (across all media)?
Have control over choice of energy supply?	nrg_supply_ctrl	5.1 Do you have any direct control over the choice of energy supply for your facility?
What proportion of energy comes from renewable sources?	nrg_supply_mix	5.2 Do you know the mix of renewable and non-renewable sources in your energy supply? If so, what percentage of your electricity is purchased on a green (renewable) tariff?
Electricity purchased by	nrg_supply_purch	5.3 Who purchases electricity on behalf of the facility?
Energy supplier has policy on low-carbon provision?	nrg_supply_pol	5.4 Does your energy supplier have a policy on the provision of low-carbon energy? Please provide details.
On-site generation/storage of energy?	on_site_nrg	5.5 Do you make use of on-site generation/storage of energy? (Not including any research on energy storage that might be conducted). If so, please provide details.
Energy monitoring tools	nrg_monitor_tool	6.1 What energy monitoring tools do you have at your disposal?
Energy usage (MWh/yr)	nrg_use_mwh_yr	6.2 Please provide an estimate of your annual energy consumption in kWh.
Max Theoretical Energy usage (MWh/yr)	nrg_use_max_mwh_yr	6.3 If your estimate of annual energy consumption is significantly different from the maximum annual energy draw, please also provide the latter.
Proportions of GHG Emission Scopes	nrg_ghg_scopes	6.5 Do you know what proportion of the energy usage of the facility sits within each of the GHG emission scopes (1, 2 and 3)? Please provide details.
Can exploit energy consumption variation over time?	variation_nrg_use	6.6 Are you able to take advantage of the variation in energy consumption over time (days or weeks)? Please give details.
Can manage the load to exploit low-carbon energy supply?	load_management	6.7 Can the system load be managed to maximise the use of low-carbon energy supply?

Efficiency metrics used	suggested_nrg_metric	6.8 Do you record/provide any efficiency metrics for your energy usage? If so, please provide details.
Power Usage Effectiveness [near 1 is best]	pue	6.9 Do you calculate the Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) for your facility? If so, what is the estimated annual value?
Opinion of PUE as efficiency metric?	effic_metrics	6.10 Do you consider that Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) is the most suitable measure of efficiency? Please share your thoughts and ideas. Please also tell us about any other metrics that you use - if possible, use terminology from Table 1 of Reddy et al
Proportions of energy consumed by each system component	detailed_nrg_cons_comp	6.11 Do you have knowledge about the proportions of energy consumption related to each component (e.g. storage, compute, networking, cooling etc.)? If so, please provide details, including whether the consumption is measured or based on information provi
Is the environmental impact considered in planning/design of new facilities?	planned_envIRON_consID	7.2 Do you take environmental considerations into account when planning and designing a new facility? If so, please provide details.
Does environmental impact affect purchasing policy?	purchase_envIRON_consID	7.3 Does your purchasing policy take into account environmental considerations? If so, please provide details.
Does environmental impact affect disposal policy?	disposal_envIRON_consID	7.4 Does your disposal policy take into account environmental considerations? If so, please provide details.
Do you require minimum knowledge level of users?	usr_knowledge	8.1 Do you require users to meet a minimum knowledge level before using your facility? Please provide details, including whether knowledge of environmental factors is included.
Budget for training related to environmental impact?	budget_training	8.2 Do you have a budget allocated to user training relating to environmental issues, energy usage and efficiency? If so, how much (in total and per user)?
Does training affect user behaviour?	training_impact	8.3 Do you think the training has a noticeable impact on user behaviour? If so, in what way? Please provide details.
Do you have info on user energy footprints, and do you provide it to users?	usr_nrg_ftprt	8.4 Do you have information on users' energy footprints? If so, do you provide that information to your users? Please provide details.
With unlimited budget, how would you optimise efficiency?	imag_user_supp	8.5 If you had an unlimited budget, what would you do to help users optimise the use of your facility in terms of energy efficiency? Please provide details.
Training needs of your team?	train_needs	9.2 What are the training needs for you and your team in terms of making progress towards Net Zero? Please provide details.
Need for standards, policies, certification to support Net Zero?	need_std_cert	9.3 Do you think there is a need for standards, policies and/or certification to make progress towards Net Zero? Please provide details.